

Clothing area factor measurements and estimations for cold-weather clothing

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Introduction

Of the various methods used for obtaining the clothing area factor (f_{cl}), 3D scanning is the most accurate. However, this method requires a skilled operator and expensive scanners along with a relatively time-intensive process [1-3]. Another method estimates the f_{cl} based on total thermal resistance (R_t) measurements. Although measurements by this method are relatively inaccurate, the overall effect on the calculated intrinsic thermal resistance (R_{cl}) is minimal [1, 2]. This study compares the f_{cl} of cold-weather clothing obtained from measurements from a 3D scanner and estimations based on R_t . Since the estimation method was developed for typical indoor clothing, the applicable range of R_{cl} is from 0.2 – 1.7 clo (1 clo = 0.155 m²K/W) [1, 2]. The cold-weather clothing examined in this study did not include clothing or equipment on the head, hands, and feet. Therefore, only one of the eight clothing configurations had an R_{cl} greater than 1.7 clo.

Methods

Scanning method—a Cyberware Whole Body (WB) scanner was utilized to acquire the 3D surface geometry of a manikin. The Cyberware WB scanner is a laser-based scanning system designed for scanning the surface of a human body. The scanning system employs four cameras to cover a 2.0 meter high and 1.2 meter diameter cylindrical volume. During the scanning process, the cameras take 17 seconds to move vertically while four horizontal laser beams sweep the surface of an object. The four 3D range images are then integrated together to represent the whole surface into a triangulated mesh structure (as shown in Figure 1).

Figure 1. Triangular mesh structure from scan (Left); scan of a cold-weather clothing configuration (Right)

The total surface area of the triangulated surface can be computed as a sum of all triangular areas, which is a trivial application of the Heron formula [5]. The accuracy of the computed surface area from a 3D scan was evaluated on two cylinders with known dimensions, producing a relative error of 0.57% and 0.18%. Estimation method—previously developed equations [2, 4] vary slightly and therefore the coefficient for R_{cl} was rounded to the nearest tenth, resulting in the following equation:

$$f_{cl} = 1 + 0.3 \cdot R_{cl}$$

Results and discussion

This study examined the f_{cl} of cold-weather garments and ensembles with R_{cl} values ranging from 0.25 – 1.88 clo. The average percent change between estimated and measured f_{cl} is 5% with the largest change being 18%. Although cold-weather clothing garments and ensembles were examined, there was no clothing or equipment on the head, hands, or feet. If a hood was included, it was not worn over the head. Therefore, R_{cl} values of seven of the eight configurations were within the applicable range for the estimation method. When using the estimation method, errors may occur for configurations with a different number of inner layers that include the same outer layer. For example, configurations H and G use the same outer layer and configurations F and D also use the same outer layer. In this case, the scanning method resulted in a difference of less than 1% in f_{cl} when using the same outer layer for both cases, while the estimation method resulted in an average of 9% difference of f_{cl} when using the same outer layer.

Figure 2. Column chart of the scanned and estimated f_{cl} values, ordered from lowest to highest R_{cl}

Conclusions

When using the estimation method, an R_{cl} within the valid range (0.2 – 1.7 clo) does not necessarily result in the most accurate estimation of f_{cl} . Configuration E is within the range and the estimation is 18% lower than the scan, while configuration H is 1.88 clo and is 8% higher than the scan. The two largest discrepancies between the estimation and the scan were from an outer layer being tested alone. More testing and analysis is required to determine if this is a consistent occurrence.

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